

Development and evaluation of andrographolide nanoemulsions for antibacterial activity against *Streptococcus* sp.

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ABSTRACT

This project aimed to synthesize andrographolide nanoemulsions using a low-energy method and compare their inhibitory effects on *Streptococcus* sp. between andrographolide nanoemulsions and andrographolide extract. Firstly, andrographolide nanoemulsions were synthesized from andrographolide extract using a low-energy method. Andrographolide extract was mixed with pure virgin coconut oil and Tween 80. The morphology of the andrographolide nanoemulsions was characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was employed to identify andrographolide. The inhibitory capacity was tested by using the zone of inhibition. The results show the average zone of inhibition is 1.35 ± 0.40 cm for andrographolide nanoemulsions and 0.31 ± 0.25 cm for regular andrographolide extract. It is found that the inhibitory effect on *Streptococcus* sp. in andrographolide nanoemulsions is more than quadrupled when compared to regular andrographolide extract. Based on the experiment, Tween 80 does not affect antibacterial activity.

KEYWORDS: Nanoemulsions, *Streptococcus* sp., Andrographolide, Sore Throat, Tween 80

1. INTRODUCTION

*Andrographis paniculata*² currently holds significant medical importance. It is a traditional Thai herb that has been used for medical purposes in Thailand for an extended period. Its properties are known to alleviate symptoms⁹ associated with the common cold, coughs, and sore throats. Extensive research and studies have provided evidence supporting its efficiency in treating respiratory infections. Tonsillitis⁴, a common respiratory⁸ disease affecting children aged 5-15 years, often necessitates the use of antibiotics due to bacterial infection, primarily involving *Streptococcus* sp. Bacterial tonsillitis requires antibiotic intervention to inhibit bacterial proliferation. However, antibiotic administration

can elicit varying adverse effects in patients, and inappropriate use may contribute to the development of antimicrobial² resistance. Consequently, there is a growing interest in utilizing traditional Thai herbs, such as *Andrographis paniculata*, for the development of pharmaceutical¹ interventions targeting respiratory ailments.

Nevertheless, conventional drug delivery systems present limitations regarding the onset of action and therapeutic efficacy of *Andrographis paniculata*. To address these limitations, the present study aims to develop an enhanced drug delivery⁶ and absorption methodology by increasing the surface area of the substance to generate nanoparticles⁷. The proposed mechanism of the action involves the targeted delivery of the drug into bacterial cells to disrupt the cell walls of *Streptococcus* sp. using andrographolide extract obtained from *Andrographis paniculata*.

This investigation employs the nanoemulsion⁵ synthesis process, which yields particles of reduced size and enhanced stability compared to conventional emulsions. In particular, this study focuses on low-energy methods¹¹ for nanoemulsion formation such as spontaneous emulsification, phase inversion composition (PIC), and phase inversion temperature (PIT) due to their advantages in energy efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and suitability for thermally sensitive compounds, including herbal extracts. These methods rely on manipulating the physicochemical properties of the system (e.g., surfactant composition and temperature) rather than using high-shear mechanical forces.

In related research by Chomchoey et al. (2023), a nanoemulsion system¹⁰ was formulated using Tween 80 at 30 g/kg as the primary surfactant and coconut oil at 100-300 g/kg as the oil phase. The formulation also incorporated lecithin at 10 g/kg, which enhanced emulsification efficiency and stability. This formulation approach demonstrated the practical effectiveness of using Tween 80 and coconut oil in low-energy nanoemulsion systems.

The incorporation of these low-energy approaches is expected to preserve the bioactivity of andrographolide while enabling the formation of stable nano-sized³ droplets, which in turn enhances drug delivery, absorption efficiency, and therapeutic potential. Thus, by synthesizing andrographolide into a nanoemulsion via low-energy methods, this study aims to provide a more rapid and efficacious alternative for treating respiratory infections particularly those caused by *Streptococcus* sp. with reduced reliance on conventional antibiotics.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Preparation of andrographolide nanoemulsion

A low-energy method was employed to synthesize the nanoemulsion from *Andrographis paniculata*. Initially, 180 mg of andrographolide extract, obtained from nine *Andrographis paniculata* tablets, was dissolved in 10 mL of 95% w/v ethanol. The resulting extract was then mixed with 5 mL of virgin coconut oil and 10 mL of the surfactant TWEEN 80. This mixture was carefully added dropwise into 25 mL of purified water using a micropipette. The aqueous phase was placed on a magnetic stirrer (IKA® C-MAG HS 7) and stirred at a speed of 800-1500 revolutions per minute (rpm) for 15 minutes to form a nanoemulsion.

2.2 Characterization of nanoemulsion

The synthesized nanoemulsion was characterized to confirm its structural and compositional properties. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM, JEOLJEM-2100) was used to examine the morphology and determine the particle size of the nanoemulsion. The presence of andrographolide in the formulation was confirmed using thin-layer chromatography (TLC) employing aluminum-backed silica gel 60 F254 TLC plates and ethanol as the solvent system, and UV-visible spectroscopy (Shimadzu UV-1800).

2.3 Antibacterial efficacy

Culture media were prepared by mixing the nutrient broth (NB) and nutrient agar (NA). The media were sterilized using an autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes. After cooling, the NA medium was poured into petri dishes, while NB was reserved for bacterial cultivation. The bacterial strain *Streptococcus* sp. was inoculated into test tubes containing nutrient broth and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The cultured bacteria were then spread on nutrient agar plates using the streak plate method and incubated for another 24 hours to facilitate bacterial growth.

Antibacterial assay the antibacterial activity was assessed using the zone of inhibition method. Each petri dish was divided into four quadrants, and a sterile filter paper disc was placed in each quadrant. The test substances applied to the discs included the andrographolide nanoemulsion, andrographolide extract, distilled water (as a negative control), and penicillin (as a positive control). A micropipette was used to dispense 2 µL of each test substance onto individual discs, ensuring that only one substance was applied per disc. The plates were incubated, and the diameter of inhibition zones was measured using a digital caliper to determine antibacterial efficacy. Each experiment was performed in 9 replicates to ensure statistical reliability and accuracy.

2.4 Safety & Ethics

Gloves and a mask were used throughout, and all biological waste, such as plant residues, culture media, and contaminated consumables, was collected separately and sterilized via autoclaving before disposal to prevent environmental contamination and the spread of microorganisms.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research demonstrates the successful synthesis of andrographolide nanoemulsions from *Andrographis paniculata* extract via a low-energy method, specifically magnetic stirring at 800 rpm for 15 minutes. Nanoemulsions exhibited particle sizes within the range of 200-500 nm (Figure 1).

Based on the thin-layer chromatography (TLC) experiment the presence of andrographolide in nanoemulsion was confirmed. The R_f value, or retention factor, is a ratio that indicates how far a compound travels on a TLC plate relative to the distance traveled by the solvent front. It is calculated by dividing the distance moved by the compound (spot distance) by the distance moved by the solvent (solvent front distance). In this experiment (Table 1), andrographolide extract showed one UV-active spot with an R_f value of 0.50 (Figure 2). The andrographolide nanoemulsion consisted of five UV-active spots, in which spot number 3 having the same R_f value as andrographolide extract. The same R_f value suggests that the active compound, andrographolide, are presented in the nanoemulsion. These findings reinforce the chemical integrity of the nanoemulsion formulation and its potential to retain the biological activity of the native extract.

Evaluation of the antibacterial efficacy of these andrographolide nanoemulsions against *Streptococcus* sp. revealed a significant enhancement compared to standard *Andrographis paniculata* extract. The andrographolide nanoemulsions yielded an average inhibition zone of 1.35 ± 0.40 cm, substantially exceeding the 0.31 ± 0.25 cm observed with the standard extract (Table 2). Furthermore, Tween 80, employed as a control, demonstrated an average inhibition zone of 0.25 ± 0.18 cm, thereby confirming that the observed antibacterial activity was solely attributable to the andrographolide nanoemulsions. Notably, the andrographolide nanoemulsions exhibited a four-fold increase in inhibitory potency against *Streptococcus* sp. relative to the standard extract.

The superior antibacterial performance of the andrographolide nanoemulsions can be attributed to their reduced particle size. This characteristic enhances the rate of cellular uptake and increases the surface area available for interaction with target cells, thereby optimizing the delivery and efficacy of the active pharmaceutical ingredient. In conclusion, this study underscores the potential of andrographolide nanoemulsions as a highly effective antibacterial agent. The employment of a low-energy synthesis method offers a facile and efficient approach to augment the therapeutic potential of

herbal extracts. This advancement may pave the way for developing novel pharmaceutical and antimicrobial products with improved efficacy.

Figure 1 (a) Andrographolide nanoemulsions observed under a transmission electron microscope. (b) The nanoemulsion exhibits particle sizes in the range of approximately 200 nm.

Figure 2 For this study, lane 1 designates the andrographolide extract, whereas lane 2 represents the andrographolide nanoemulsions. (a) TLC was observed under UV light. (b) TLC was marked to identify the position of andrographolide.

Table 1 R_f value from TLC of andrographolide nanoemulsion

Spot	distance (cm)	R_f
1	2.60	0.31
2	3.70	0.45
3 (andrographolide)	4.10	0.50
4	5.10	0.61
5	5.75	0.69
Solvent front	8.25	

Table 2 Average zone of inhibition

Substance	Zone of inhibition \pm SD (cm)
RO water (negative control)	0.00
penicillin (positive control)	2.01 ± 0.85
andrographolide nanoemulsion	1.35 ± 0.40
andrographolide extract	0.31 ± 0.25
Tween 80	0.25 ± 0.18

4. CONCLUSIONS

The andrographolide nanoemulsion was successfully synthesized using a low-energy method by employing a magnetic stirrer. The resulting nanoparticles ranged in size from 20 to 200 nm. Furthermore, the andrographolide nanoemulsion exhibited four times greater antibacterial efficacy against *Streptococcus* sp. compared to the andrographolide extract. These findings support the potential application of nanoemulsions in pharmaceutical and cosmetic products, such as mouthwashes or topical medications. Moreover, they may contribute to addressing the issue of antibiotic resistance by integrating nanotechnology with herbal medicines.

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Author Contributions

P.C. and S.N. were responsible for the experimental design and implementation. In addition, they collected experimental data and conducted data analysis. P.C. authored the research report and performed statistical interpretation of the results. S.N. reviewed the content for accuracy and edited the final version of the research manuscript. Lastly, T.Y. designed the graphics and produced the presentation video for the project.

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7. REFERENCES

- 1 Jaiswal, M., Dudhe, R., & Sharma, P. K. (2015). Nanoemulsion: An advanced mode of drug delivery system. *3 Biotech*, 5(2), 123–127. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-014-0214-0>
- 2 Hu, D., Ogawa, K., Kajiyama, M., & Enomae, T. (2020). Characterization of self-assembled silver nanoparticle ink based on nanoemulsion method. *Open Science*, 7, 200296. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.200296>
- 3 Misra, Parveen, S., R., & Sahoo, S. K. (2012). Nanoparticles: A boon to drug delivery, therapeutics, diagnostics, and imaging. *Nanomedicine: Nanotechnology, Biology and Medicine*, 8(2), 147–166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nano.2011.05.016>
- 4 National Cancer Institute. (n.d.). *Andrographis paniculata*. https://www.nci.go.th/en/research/researchdivision/research_informationfarthalai.html
- 5 Pongpisitsan, K. (2006). *Extraction of active compounds from Andrographis paniculata using ethyl alcohol* [Master's thesis, Kasetsart University] https://doi.nrct.go.th/ListDoi/listDetail?Resolve_Doi=10.14457/KU.the.2006.561
- 6 Salingam, N., & Chamchong, M. (2012). *Nanoemulsion of essential oil from clove flower prepared by aqueous titration method* (9th ed.). Kasetsart University, Kamphaeng Saen Campus.
- 7 Singh, Y., Meher, J. G., Raval, K., Khan, F. A., Chaurasia, M., Jain, N. K., & Chourasia, M. K. (2017). Nanoemulsion: Concepts, development, and applications in drug delivery. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 252, 28–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2017.03.008>
- 8 Thamchat, T. (2012). *Andrographis paniculata*. *Kasetsart Livestock Journal*, 2012(153), 24–30.
- 9 Wantong, N. (2016). *Management of acute pharyngitis* [Bachelor's thesis]. Ubon Ratchathani University.
- 10 Chomchoey, N., Tongchitpakdee, S., & Tontul, I. (2023). Fabrication and characterization of nanoemulsions for encapsulation and delivery of vitexin: Antioxidant activity, storage stability and in vitro digestibility. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 103(6), 2532-2543. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.12375>
- 11 Safaya M, & Rotliwala Y.C. (2020). Nanoemulsions: A review on low energy formulation methods, characterization, applications and optimization technique. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 320, 114461. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2019.11.267>